

METHODOLOGY OF PREPARING VOCATIONAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF THE DUAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The article presents information on the integration processes of further expanding the integrative organizational function of education, modernization of forms and methods of education, and the formation of personal and professional qualities based on ensuring the harmony and coherence of innovative professional potential elements in the further development of the trend of the theory and practice of vocational education.

The development of human civilization in the world is characterized by very complex and contradictory processes and trends. Achievements in science, engineering and technology serve to radically improve the quality of life of people, while creating social, economic, cultural, material and technical and other conditions for their vital activity, as well as realizing their personal needs and interests.

Mobile communications, personal computers, personal appliances and all types of service equipment, modern information and communication networks are based on the scientific and technological progress of mankind, and today, in the context of technical changes, the artificial living environment is becoming more efficient than the natural environment.

According to international experience, deepening the organic connection of general vocational and specialized disciplines with production structures has a positive effect on the effectiveness of education. Also, in the further development of the trend of the theory and practice of vocational education, such integration processes as further expanding the integrative organizational function of education based on ensuring the harmony and coherence of innovative professional potential elements, modernization of forms and methods of education, and the formation of personal and professional qualities play an important role. This is achieved by checking the results of training vocational education specialists and employees of production enterprises for professional activity on the basis of the dual education system, taking into account the principles of coherence and interdependence, using pedagogical diagnostic methods, and developing appropriate methodological recommendations on the identified problems and requires the expansion of information didactic possibilities of educational integration.

Laws and trends of implementation, development and trends of interdisciplinarity, integration of science and production in the process of vocational education in professional educational institutions, problems of training teachers of vocational education for professional,

pedagogical and production activities based on the dual education system, pedagogical diagnostics of professional training theoretical, conceptual and technological. Although the basics have been studied to a certain extent, the didactic possibilities of the integration of general and specialized subjects in the training of vocational education specialists, based on an integrative approach. The need to develop and implement educational and methodological support and scientific and methodological foundations of teaching determines the relevance of the present day.

When studying the continuity factor from the perspective of vocational education, supporters of this approach single out three directions of possible human movement in the field of continuous education. They are:

1. Improving professional qualifications and professional skills at the stages and levels of vocational education without changing the level of vocational education;
2. Gradual ascent, taking into account the needs and capabilities of the individual, as well as the socio-economic conditions in society;
3. Improving professional qualifications associated with changing the direction of education, taking into account the changes.

The main goal of vocational education is to train highly qualified, competitive in the labor market, knowledgeable, responsible, knowledgeable in their profession and capable of operating in interrelated fields, able to work effectively in their specialty at the level of world standard requirements, capable of continuous professional growth, social and professional mobility, as well as to meet individual needs in obtaining appropriate education.

Nowadays, the innovative development of scientific and technical progress, the rapid renewal of knowledge require future specialists to quickly adapt to modern conditions and strive to acquire educational and cognitive motives. This creates the need for future specialists to independently research, independently solve professional problems, creatively approach them, and at the same time actively acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications in the production process based on the unity of theory and practice. Therefore, today the process of training active, inquisitive, intellectual, capable of management, professionally cultured, competitive, creatively thinking specialists is one of the most important tasks of the continuous education system, and in this regard, improving the preparation of future technical mechanical specialists and production workers for professional activity in vocational educational institutions based on the dual education system is of great scientific and practical importance. It is noted that the development of the theoretical foundations of building a dual system of training technical mechanical specialists for professional activity in vocational educational institutions is based on a number of requirements. They are:

- basing educational goals on the needs of social production;
- organizational approach to the socio-philosophical, scientific worldview foundations of educational activities;
- reliance on the didactic foundations of the methodological nature of vocational education.

The clarification of the main, conceptually significant ideas that meet these requirements is carried out on the basis of principles of “internal”, phenomenological and methodological, as well as socio-pedagogical nature, which have a decisive influence on the development of vocational education as a special integrative area of vocational education.

For the construction of a dual system of vocational education in vocational educational institutions, the rule that continuous vocational education allows for the optimal integration of humanistic principles with the needs of the production sector and society is of conceptual importance.

In fact, based on the methodological nature of professional education, the third idea of conceptual importance, which ensures the feasibility of building a dual system of professional education, can be explained as follows: dual restructuring of the educational system in the process of professional training of engineer-pedagogue personnel ensures the integrative nature of professional education, expressing its systemic integrity.

It can be concluded that these distinguished conceptually important ideas ensure the methodological integrity of the value-purpose (axiological), meaningful-organizational (ontological) and technological foundations of creating a dual system of professional education, and they are the theoretical-methodological basis of conceptual modeling of education, as a result of which a dual system conceptual model of professional education was developed.

We distinguished three levels of expression of the dual system of professional education: methodological level, functional-technological level and personal result level.

1. Methodological level - more precisely, the methodological principles reflected in the construction and operation of the professional education system and methodological tools corresponding to them: reflecting the features of the formation of any educational system, ensuring their structural and functional integrity, interaction and connection between the components that make them up general methodological principles and tools; special methodological principles that reflect the essence of the systematic organization of professional education as a specific field of education; principles of construction and implementation of professional education as an educational field with a special type.

2. Active technological level - in the course of professional education, a dual transformation of engineering activity into pedagogical activity is carried out on a technological basis, reflecting the systematic and procedural aspect of education. It has a secondary content construction: in the field of education, it is continuous improvement of personal and professional competence of teachers and students; in the field of production - continuous development of personal professional competence of specialists. In the system forming this dual system, the legal frameworks, organizational forms and didactic conditions of the educational process for professional training are different.

3. Personal result level - reflects the subjective result aspect of education, which is general for both structural systems and reflects personal professional competence of the specialist formed during the education process.

The dual system of professional education is an innovative type of organization of professional education, which provides for the interrelated development of education and production areas for the training of specialists, and it is built on the basis of these three methodological foundations: axiological (parity of humanistic and technical aspects), ontological (competent approach), technological (organization of the development of socio-professional relations in professional activity).

The dual system of professional education in professional educational institutions requires the practical development of a conceptual model in determining didactic conditions,

which reflects the construction of the conceptual-theoretical foundations of the dual system of training technical and mechanical personnel in professional education, as well as the systemic-component features of the educational process, and their interdependence and relevance.

In conclusion, it should be said that, according to modern systemic-pedagogical ideas, the educational process is a systemically interconnected and purposeful interaction of the following components: goals of activity, teacher, student, content of activity, forms of activity, means and methods of activity, result of activity. Technological organization of socio-professional relations in the educational process (in the study group, in production practice, etc.). The dual system of vocational education is associated with the practical organization of the development of the structure and content of professional training in a vocational educational institution in accordance with the conceptual - theoretical and didactic foundations.

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